

Fast XML/HTML for Haskell: XML TypeLift and improved Xeno

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Abstract. The paper presents and compares a range of parsers with and without data mapping for conversion between XML and Haskell. The best performing parser competes favorably with the fastest tools available in other languages and is, thus, suitable for use in large-scale data analysis. The best performing parser also allows software developers of intermediate-level Haskell programming skills to start processing large numbers of XML documents soon after finding the relevant XML Schema from a simple internet search, without the need for specialist prior knowledge or skills. We hope that this unique combination of parser performance and usability will provide a new standard for XML mapping to high-level languages.

1 Introduction

XML is the current dominant format for document interchange, being optimized for long-term schema evolution and extensibility[1–4]. Importantly, XML is based on a number of different data formats, most of which are of practical and commercial interest. That is because they allow system evolution over long time span (in case of PDB[4] since 1976, in case of FixML since 1992[5].)

This report will review the latest developments in the generation of efficient parsers in Haskell. Haskell is a high-level language that incorporates parsing plain XML of unknown format at a speed that is comparable with leading parsers already available in low-level languages. Haskell also automatically generates high-level representations of document content from XML Schema, the current dominant schema description language for XML.

Being a sister language to HTML, XML benefits from HTML’s data model. Furthermore, many tools are available to convert HTML to XML syntax and processes; XPath[6] and XQuery[7] are two such tools.

1.1 Use of XML

Having been widely accepted and adopted as the standard for transmission and data storage, XML’s self-descriptive tree structure confers two important user benefits: simplified and standardized data processing. By storing data in plain text format, XML facilitates simple data sharing, transport, and historical storage, without encountering any hardware, software or platform compatibility

37 problems. Importantly, XML offers operational compatibility through its com-
38 mon syntax to enable transfer of messages across communication systems of
39 differing formats.

40 The generation of significant volumes of XML data has initiated a wealth of
41 active research into rapid parsing[8–10].

42 1.2 XML Schema

43 The overall XML domain is vast, with individual XML file formats being tailored
44 to specific needs and applications. While XML’s self-descriptive structure and file
45 format allows information to be easily ingested, most application areas require
46 strict validation rules to ensure the logical correctness of XML documents.

47 In 2001, the W3C formally recommended the XML Schema[11] for the de-
48 scription and validation of XML document structure and content by defining
49 document elements, attributes and data types. As extensive-type descriptions,
50 XSDs are helpful for standardizing the large number of XML formats in current
51 use. They do this not only by defining document structure and elements, but also
52 by setting out formal requirements for document validation. Most W3C XML
53 formats have XML Schema definitions that have been developed and standard-
54 ized by ISO/IEC; the same applies for all ECMA standards, including Microsoft
55 Open-XML and the LibreOffice OpenDocument format.

56 For newcomers to the field, we now summarize key features of XML Schema:

- 57 – representation of XML documents with:
 - 58 • `<xs:element>` for XML elements with cardinality constraints, such as
 - 59 `minOccurs=0`, and `maxOccurs=5`;
 - 60 • `<xs:attribute>` for XML attributes;
 - 61 • content representation as regular trees composed of nested
 - 62 * `<xs:sequence>` for a number of elements in a fixed order;
 - 63 * `<xs:choice>` for when any of a number of elements (or `<xs:sequence>`
 - 64 entries) may be given;
 - 65 * `<xs:all>` for a fixed sequence of elements in any order;
 - 66 * `mixed="true"` for situations where a given sequence of elements may
 - 67 be interwoven with free-form text;
- 68 – rich, named types:
 - 69 • number of predefined types with ISO-standards for text representations;
 - 70 • `xs:any` type for when arbitrary XML fragments must be embedded;
 - 71 • distinction between `xs:text` and identifier type `xs:token`;
 - 72 • syntactic distinction of flat types (`<simpleContent>`) and tree fragment
 - 73 types (`<complexContent>`);
- 74 – typical programming language facilities:
 - 75 • namespace management for target elements;
 - 76 • extensive comments with `<xs:annotate>`;
- 77 – data modeling by cross-references:

- 78 • element identifiers and references (`ref="id"`), so that the same element
- 79 can be used in different document locations;
- 80 • `<xs:group>` for groups of elements or attributes that are commonly
- 81 found together;
- 82 • ability to restrict the value of any type to a subset, implementing `<xs:restriction>`
- 83 as a list of values, or a regular expression pattern;
- 84 • ability to form object-oriented hierarchy of types, where `xs:extension`
- 85 adds new attributes, and append further content in `xs:sequence` or pro-
- 86 vide for alternatives with `xs:choice` (`xs:sequence` cannot be extended
- 87 with `xs:choice`, and vice-versa);
- 88 • `xs:key` and `xs:unique` constraints that record cross-references within
- 89 the document, and provide XPath-like expressions for validation.

90 1.3 Previous work on parsing XML in Haskell

91 Two current approaches exist for programming XML document processing sys-
 92 tems when using functional languages such as Haskell[12]. In the first approach,
 93 the XML document takes a tree-like structure that then forms the basis for de-
 94 signing a library of combinators that perform generic XML document processing
 95 tasks: selection, generation and transformation of document trees. The second
 96 approach uses a type translation framework that is similar to *object-relational*
 97 *mapping* frameworks; this allows idiomatic XML schemas to be translated into
 98 idiomatic Haskell data declarations.

99 In response to the large number of diverse XML datasets that are in current
 100 use, there has, to date, been a wealth of rich research into the efficiency of XML
 101 data set ingestion[13–19].

102 Haskell’s many packages for manipulating XML data sets include

- 103 – `xml-conduit` [20]: provides streamed parsing and rendering functions for
- 104 XML.
- 105 – `HaXML` [21]: a collection of utilities that use Haskell for parsing, filtering,
- 106 transforming and generating XML documents. The utilities include an XML
- 107 parser and validator, a stream parser for XML events, a combinator library
- 108 and two translators, once of which translates from DTD to Haskell and
- 109 another which translates from XML Schema definitions to Haskell data types
- 110 (both translators include associated parsers and pretty printers).
- 111 – `XsdToHaskell` [21]: an `HaXML` tool to translate valid XML Schema defini-
- 112 tions into equivalent Haskell types, together with `SchemaType` instances.
- 113 – `hxt` (`Haskell XML Toolbox` [22]): a collection of Haskell tools for XML pro-
- 114 cessing whose core component is a domain-specific language with a set of
- 115 combinators for XML tree processing. Although based on `HaXml`, `hxt` uses
- 116 a generic data model to represent XML documents, including the DTD sub-
- 117 set and the document subset, in Haskell.
- 118 – `hexml`[23]: a fast, DOM-style XML parser that parses only a subset of the
- 119 XML. This parser skips entities and does not support `<!DOCTYPE`-related
- 120 features.

121 – xeno[24]: a fast, low-memory use, event-based XML parser, written in pure
122 Haskell. A key feature is that it includes an SAX [25]-style parser, which
123 triggers events such as tags and attributes.

124 1.4 The need for high performance parser generators

125 Here, we aim to develop a practical, high-performance XML parser, possibly by
126 compromising on strict conformance to XML namespaces, and avoiding strict
127 validation.

128 Since no pre-existing XML document validation tools exist, our novel parser
129 will enable fast and safe parsing of multiple large XML documents in order to
130 perform analyses, and to update databases. The only existing parsing applica-
131 tions that have similar functionality to our target parser are Protein Databank,
132 which has over 166 thousand depositions [4, 26, 27]¹, and real-time processing
133 of FixML [5] messages.

134 A secondary aim of our work is that the majority of programmers should
135 not need to consider the complexity of parsing inputs; this will be achieved by
136 abstracting the parser in such a way as to avoid low-level drudgery.

137 2 Usage

138 To demonstrate the practical use of `xml-typelift`, we here give an example of
139 a simplified `user.xml` document that conforms to the `user.xsd` XML Schema.

140 As a test case, we present code that prints the contents of the name element.
141 Typical XML Schema:

```
<xs:schema
  xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema">
  <xs:element name='users' >
    <xs:complexType>
      <xs:sequence>
        <xs:element name="user" type="UserType"
                    minOccurs="0"
                    maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
      </xs:sequence>
    </xs:complexType>
  </xs:element>

  <xs:complexType name="UserType" mixed="false">
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="uid" type="xs:int"/>
      <xs:element name="name" type="xs:string"/>
      <xs:element name="bday" type="xs:date"
                    minOccurs="0"/>
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:schema>
```

¹ Developed between 1976 and early 2020.

```
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:schema>
```

142 An example document would be:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<users> <user>
  <uid>123</uid>
  <name>John</name>
  <bday>1990-11-12</bday>
</user>
</users>
```

143 2.1 Parsing XML with DOM

144 Here, we present an example program that returns a list of all `<name>` nodes in
145 the input document:

```
import Xeno.DOM
import qualified Data.ByteString as BS

processFile filename = do
  Right result <- BS.readFile filename
  >>= Xeno.parse.inp
  print $ filter isName $ allNodes result
  where
    isName node =
      BS.toLower (Xeno.name n) == "name"
```

146 This code is recommended in circumstances that require an HTML parsing
147 engine that is faster than those commonly available in Python [28]².

148 2.2 Parsing XML documents in an event-based manner

149 The `Xeno.SAX` parser follows the SAX [25] model of XML parsing, whereby the
150 input is scanned. Rather than returning tokens, `Xeno.SAX` calls back upon finding
151 a critical point in the input, with pointers to string values.

152 The callback set can be represented by the following Haskell data structure:

² Here, we assume that an HTML document properly quotes attributes; if this assumption is not valid, the attributes are skipped by the parser. We can easily develop a fast HTML parser by using the version of `Xeno.DOM.Robust` that automatically closes tags. Note that, in the authors' experience, it usually suffices to simply analyze webpage content.

```

data Process a = Process {
    openF    :: ByteString -> a
  , attrF   :: ByteString -> ByteString -> a
  , endOpenF :: ByteString -> a
  , textF   :: ByteString -> a
  , closeF  :: ByteString -> a
  , cdataF  :: ByteString -> a }
process :: (Monad m, VectorizedString str)
    => Process (m ()) -> str -> m ()

```

153 This method of processing not only induces *inversion of control*, but also
154 makes the program more difficult to understand. It does, however, result in
155 faster code, especially when callbacks can be statically inlined, as is usually the
156 case.

157 In order to simplify the definition of new parsers, we propose reification of
158 the callback set into a record. If our parser needs only to process text nodes, then
159 we can use a default instance that does nothing, and redefine textF callback as
160 follows:

```

textPrinter = def { textF = putStrLn }

```

161 Event-based parsers are based on the concept of passing a function record
162 with callbacks; in practical terms, this mode of parsing is inconvenient.

163 In the code below, we utilize an ST monad that maintains an imperative
164 state under purely functional wraps [29], thus creating a reference for keeping
165 the current output with newSTRefs.

```

import          Xeno.SAX                as Xeno
import qualified Data.ByteString        as BS
import qualified Data.ByteString.Lazy  as BSL
import          Data.Default (def)

processFile filename = do
    input  <- BS.readFile filename
    allPres <- stToIO $ do
        results <- newSTRef ([] :: BSL.ByteString)
        current  <- newSTRef ([] :: BS.ByteString)
        selected <- newSTRef False

```

166 For each event, we update the partial output reference.

167 Note that, in this case, when opening openF of a new XML element <name>,
168 we are in the selected fragment when closing closeF of the XML element
169 </name>. Also, note that we are outside the selected fragment for each text
170 node textF, and we verify whether we are within the selected fragment, ap-
171 pending it to the results whenever the verification is positive.

```

let openF bs@(BS.toLower -> "name") =
    case bs of

```

```

        BS.PS _ start len ->
            writeSTRef selected True
    openF _ = return ()
    textF t = do
        isSelected <- readSTRef selected
        when isSelected $
            modifySTRef current (t:)
    closeF bs@(BS.toLower -> "name") = do
        content <- BSL.fromChunks . reverse
            <$> readSTRef current
        modifySTRef' results (content:)
        writeSTRef current []

```

172 Having now built the event handlers, the final step is to call the actual parser
 173 with the record of event handlers:

```

        Xenon.process (def {openF, closeF, textF})
            input
        readSTRef results

```

174 After calling the parser, we read the final result using the function `readSTRef`.

175 2.3 Obtaining fully typed outputs using parser generators

176 It is easy to obtain fully typed Haskell representations from XML Schema. The
 177 user must first find the XML Schema that describes the input format on the
 178 internet standard or from an XML schema repository.

179 Next, the XML Schema is handed to **XML Typelift**, which generates a
 180 Haskell module that describes both parser and mapping to Haskell ADT:

```
$ xml-typelift-cli --schema InputSchema.xsd --output InputSchema.hs
```

181 We then immediately test the generated parser and examine the output struc-
 182 ture:

```
$ runghc InputSchema.hs input.xml
```

183 The obtained result is then used by the programmer to determine how to
 184 access parsed data structure in the specific program. Specifically, XML TypeLift
 185 uses a name generation monad [30] to ensure that the resulting code is readable
 186 and comprehensible for Haskell programmers of intermediate skill level.

187 It is easier to process an example generated ADT than an original XML
 188 Schema:

```

data Users = Users { users: [User] }
data User  = User  { uid  :: Int, name :: String, bday :: Maybe Date }

```

189 This ADT is easily read by the standard parser interface from a generated
190 module:

```
parse :: ByteString -> Either String Users
```

191 We can, therefore, use it to extract the data in an example user program:

```
import UsersSchema(parse, Users(..))
processFile filename = do
  Right users <- BS.readFile filename >>= parse
  print $ map name users
```

192 This interface is preferable, and we will now explain how to ensure that it's
193 speed is comparable to the DOM and SAX approaches.

194 3 Performance techniques

195 3.1 Code generation as a scalable method of fast parsing

196 Code generation has an undeserved reputation for producing arcane code that
197 is difficult to read, due to its algorithmic origin; this raises concerns regarding
198 the malicious use of code generation [31]. In this context, we make a specific
199 effort to ensure that our parser generator is easy to read and, thus, properly
200 accessible and customizable. To do this, we first use an abstract interface to the
201 input string; this allows future parser enhancement by vectorization using the
202 `VectorizedString` class.

203 Since XML TypeLift originated from Xeno, we now discuss performance tech-
204 niques for both libraries together; we generate independent code using the same
205 performance techniques as before, before backporting them to Xeno.

206 **Splitting and representing tokens** Conventionally, parsers start by distin-
207 guishing tokens and keywords in the input, and then selecting an efficient rep-
208 resentation for them. This can be achieved by making an ADT data structure
209 or a hash table that maps each token type to an integer code. Since, in XML,
210 key tokens are identifiers and text fragments, we choose to take advantage of
211 the `ByteString` library to represent their content as two offsets³ into the input
212 string. C

213 Capitalizing on the tradition of fast XML parsing in the SAX [25] model,
214 we implicitly represent tokens by distinguishing callback functions that process
215 each token; we expect these functions to be duly inlined by the Haskell compiler.

³ The beginning and the end

216 **Performant string representation** Haskell programs use the ByteString li-
217 brary⁴, which examines large input strings efficiently by reducing each object to:
218 (a) a foreign pointer to the input; (b) an offset to the beginning of the string in
219 the input; (c) and an offset to the end of the string in the input.

220 When using this data structure for fast parsing of a known input, we add a
221 null byte to the end so that it is not necessary to check that no offsets transcend
222 the input end. Additionally, by factoring out a class of string representations
223 that allow efficient scanning, interested programmers can find even more efficient
224 representations that offer a safe interface.

225 For our specific purposes of parsing source XML documents, we wish to
226 parse both UTF-16 and UTF-8 string representations without needing to write
227 a large library variant to the ByteString library. An additional benefit of this
228 input representation is its time-saving nature compared to mapping from a file.
229 Whenever this read-only structure is unnecessary, the operating system purges
230 any relevant pages from memory, since the runtime system simply interprets those
231 pages as a large foreign object that has no pointers and, therefore, not worthy
232 of collecting. This turns out to be important, since our benchmarks show that
233 most of our parser prototypes were limited by garbage collector performance.

234 *Vectorized string interface class* Careful examination reveals that only five op-
235 erations are necessary for fast XML parsing, so that it compiles well to yield fast
236 Low Level Virtual Machine (LLVM) code:

```
class VectorizedString where
  s_index :: str -> Int -> Char
  -- | Find the first occurrence
  elemIndexFrom :: Char -> str -> Int -> Maybe Int
  -- | Extract substring between offsets
  substring :: str -> Int -> Int -> str
  -- | Move cursor forward
  drop :: Int -> str -> str
  -- | Is the output exhausted
  null :: str -> Bool
```

237 These operations are easy to define for strings and they provide a fixed *min-*
238 *imal* interface that allows for easy optimization by the compiler. Regarding en-
239 coding, they assume, for optimal implementation, that:

- 240 – any given character has a unique representation that does not overlap with
- 241 the encoding of other characters (possibly multibyte) (for scanning with
- 242 `elemIndexFrom`);
- 243 – instance is able to perform $O(1)$ -indexing, similar to an array with `s_index`;
- 244 – low-overhead operations on the **cursor** to the immutable string:
 - 245 • shift forward with `drop`,

⁴ Haskell programs also use ‘text’, which is ByteString’s spiritual successor.

- 246 • extract a substring that can be returned to the user with a substring (or
247 alternatively taking prefix with `take`), and
- 248 • scan rapidly for a token boundary character such as `<`, `>`, or `"`, which
249 can be vectorized by the compiler.

250 The unique UTF-8[32] and UTF-16 [33] encodings satisfy this set of assump-
251 tions since it is not possible to mistake single word encoding of an ASCII char-
252 acter with words that are parts of multibyte encodings.

253 We implemented these `VectorizedString` `str` type class in Haskell for a number
254 of different string representations:

- 255 – UTF-8 with both (i) classical `ByteString`, and (ii) `ByteString` with guaran-
256 teed termination by `\NUL` character. Case (ii) is faster than case (i) since it
257 does not check the range of `xxx`.
- 258 – UTF-16, while offering a less memory efficient document representation, al-
259 lows direct memory-mapping of files stored in UTF-16.

260 The ease with which these string representations can be implemented offers
261 hope that it is easy to apply SIMD vectorization as a next step.⁵

262 *Null character termination* When considering `ByteString` efficiency, one should
263 notice that our parsing scans are performed by `elemIndexFrom`; the interface
264 can, thus, be enhanced by implementing implicit termination. Since we expect
265 most of our input data to be large, adding zero at the end and allocating a
266 single segment of unreadable virtual memory just after the `ByteString` would
267 offer an acceptable tradeoff to the increased parsing speed for inputs of size in
268 the megabyte to gigabyte range.

269 Thus, `elemIndexFrom` starts checking for either a given character or null
270 termination of a given length.

271 **Compressed output tree** Large XML documents produce huge data struc-
272 tures that significantly increase garbage collection time. Since the data struc-
273 tures are usually read-only, we opt to take a shortcut, as now described. First,
274 we encode strings as offsets to the input string; this is typical when using the
275 `ByteString` library. Next, we create a large array of **offsets** (not pointers) in the
276 original input; these offsets replace all other possible pointers. Therefore, any
277 cell in the offset array encodes one of the following options:

- 278 – offset into the `ByteString` input to represent identifiers, `text()` nodes, or
279 attribute values;
- 280 – a number of sub-elements, to represent a sequence of nodes.

281 Since Haskell records are created lazily, and they are usually recycled imme-
282 diately after examination, compressing the output significantly reduces memory
283 use. We consider the creation and interpretation of this offset structure in more
284 detail below.

⁵ This is a task for future work by an interested open-source contributor.

Fig. 1: Example of XML and the offset array

285 The *offset array* structure provides a safe alternative to the PugiXML [34]
 286 method of inserting pointers inside the parsed structure that is already in place.

287 3.2 Parsing XML Schema

288 XML Schemas are frequently long and complex, typically using thousands of lines
 289 of code. It is, therefore, critical that our parser can be generated automatically
 290 from existing sources.

291 **Modeling XML Schema in Haskell** Since we aim to ingest data quickly
 292 without validating the document, the current version of XML Typelift ignores
 293 the following features: (I) comments, (II) syntactic type distinctions, (III) value
 294 restrictions that are not enumerations, and (IV) uniqueness constraints.

295 We reduce the type representations to those that are modeled within Haskell
 296 abstract data types via the following features: (a) `xs:choice` is naturally modeled
 297 by types with alternative type constructors; (b) `xs:sequence` and the set
 298 of `xs:attributes` are both modeled by record fields within a single constructor;
 299 (c) references are modeled as record fields to facilitate code re-use; (d) cardinality
 300 constraints are simplified to distinguish between a single value, `a`, an optional
 301 value, `Maybe a`, and a list `[a]`; (e) built-in types are translated into Haskell types
 302 by predefinition; (f) type restrictions are modeled depending on the constraint:
 303 (I) enumerations are modeled as set of nullary constructors, and (II) other con-
 304 straints are reduced to type aliases.

305 This is essentially an XML \leftrightarrow Haskell mapping similar to Object \leftrightarrow Relational
 306 and Object \leftrightarrow XML mappings, both of which are used for SQL and XML databases,
 307 without constraining the realm of XML types on the input.⁶

⁶ Except for mixed types, which can be modeled as a list of values with a type that has an added constructor `TextValue String`. The authors are not currently able to support this.

308 Automated type generation not only allows us to significantly decrease com-
309 plexity when writing efficient parsers for existing formats, but it also results in
310 a more convenient API that can be used in Haskell. We propose using the same
311 code generator for other target languages in our future work.

312 However, since XML Schema’s own schema is very complex, we use an *in-*
313 *intermediate representation* to describe XML document types in sufficient detail
314 to allow parsing, while at the same time omitting most of the details of schema
315 representation.⁷

316 **Schema representation** The entire XML schema can be represented as an
317 environment that holds both simple and complex declared types. In addition to
318 this environment, we also list element types that are allowed to occur in the
319 document root; this uniform representation simplifies a multitude of distinctions
320 that are made by XML Schema between types that are allowed in attributes, and
321 those are allowed only as elements. Thus, further analysis and code generation
322 are both greatly simplified.

```
data Schema = Schema { types :: Map String Type, tops :: [Element] }
```

323 For each element type, we keep track of its possible multiplicity, name, at-
324 tributes and content type; note that we ignore name spaces due to limited im-
325 plementation resources.

326 Describing element types

```
data Element = Element { eType :: Type
    minOccurs :: Int      -- 0 for no limit
    , maxOccurs :: Maybe Int -- Nothing for no limit
    , eName     :: String, targetNamespace :: NamespaceName }
```

327 *Handling of type extensions* Although simple and complex types that have either
328 simple or complex content are one of most complicated aspects of specification,
329 they can be easily modeled by either a `ComplexType` entry, reference, or modifi-
330 cation of another `ComplexType`.

```
data Type = Ref String
    | Restriction { base :: String, restricted :: Restriction }
    | Extension   { base :: String, mixin     :: Type }
    | Complex     { mixed :: Bool,  attrs     :: [Attr]
    , inner      :: TyPart }
```

331 Consistent with the principles of data mapping, whereby we seek a common
332 type for shared parts of the data structure, we avoid duplication of fields defined
333 in the base type when generating declarations of extending types.

⁷ Indeed, our approach is mirrored by the existence of other schema languages that aim to simplify XML Schema. For example, RelaxNG [17], which aims to describe regular trees inside a document.

334 *Type restrictions* Although it is easy to expand restrictions, for the time-being
335 we consider only those that need special mapping to Haskell ADT:

```
data Restriction = Enum [String] | ...
```

336 For simplicity, we omit treatment of element references and namespaces,
337 which can simply be added to a reference dictionary. Furthermore, complex
338 identifier types can be dealt with in post-parsing analysis to find the namespace
339 of each identifier.

340 *Representing element children* Types are described by regular expression in lan-
341 guage whereby letters form child elements. Here again, we use Group as a refer-
342 ence to another TyPart:

```
data TyPart = Seq [TyPart] | Choice [TyPart] | All [TyPart]  
            | Group String | Elt Element
```

343 Note that, since XML Schema allows Choice, All, and Seq⁸ to be nested,
344 the XML data declaration must be broken down into smaller sections.

345 *XML data structure flattening* It is necessary to flatten the XML data struc-
346 ture by breaking types down into sections that can be translated directly into
347 single Haskell data declarations. This is achieved by grouping the types into the
348 following categories, according to complexity:

- 349 1. those that can be implemented as type aliases (*newtypes*);
- 350 2. those that can be implemented as a single Haskell ADT declaration; and
- 351 3. those that must be split into multiple types.

352 As an example of a type that must be split into multiple types, here we
353 consider an element that contains a fixed group of children, and one variant
354 child; for simplicity, element types are omitted.

```
<xs:element name="person">  
  <xs:sequence>  
    <xs:element name="firstName"  
                minOccurs="1" maxOccurs="1"/>  
    <xs:element name="lastName"  
                minOccurs="1" maxOccurs="1"/>  
    <xs:choice>  
      <xs:element name="residentialAddress"  
                  minOccurs="1"  
                  maxOccurs="unbounded"/>  
      <xs:element name="phoneNumber"  
                  minOccurs="1"  
                  maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
```

⁸ Described as: xs:choice, xs:all, and xs:sequence.

```

        <xs:element name="imName"/>
    </xs:choice>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:element>

```

355 This can be translated into two levels of Haskell ADTs:

```

data Person = Person {
    firstName, lastName :: Text
    , residentialAddressOr :: ResidentialAddressOr }
data ResidentialAddressOr = ResidentialAddress Text
    | PhoneNumber Text          | IMName          Text

```

356 3.3 Searching for the best parser

357 Here, we describe and analyze the performance of a variety of generated code
358 types. We keep running prototypes in the repository in the `bench/proto` direc-
359 tory.⁹

360 **Parser 1** For Parser 1, we first generate an `Xeno.DOM` structure, and we convert
361 the resulting tree fragments into Haskell records using a lazy conversion.

362 **Parser 2** A continuation passing monad (`ContT`) is used for Parser 2. The pro-
363 cessor is given as a continuation that receives individual SAX events, and
364 continues processing. Next, a control flow separates out the different gener-
365 ated types, with unfinished elements held in a stack. Data is then passed to
366 the input using an asynchronous queue to allow asynchronous (and possibly
367 chunked) input processing.

```

data SAXEvent = OpenElt XMLString
    | CloseElt XMLString
    | Attr XMLString XMLString
    | ...
newtype SAXStream = SAXStream [SAXEvent]

```

368 This, in theory, allows for easier streaming through `Conduit`[35], `Pipe`[36] or
369 `Streamly`'s `Stream`, as well as incremental input processing.

370 **Parser 3** For Parser 3, a vector pointer structure, similar to `Xeno.DOM`, is cre-
371 ated. In order to reduce memory requirements, this structure is customized
372 to have fixed indices for each attribute or element that lands in the same
373 field as the constructed Haskell record.

374 **Parser 4** Parser 4 explicitly inlines string comparison by using a standard
375 parser that parses all sequence elements before constructing the output
376 record.

⁹ Interested readers are referred to the source repository so that they can compare with their prototypes and preferred optimization.

Table 1: Speed comparison for generated parser and its prototypes. Columns represent time (in seconds) required to process input file according to file size (in Mb).

1	0.99	1.97	3.78	7.61	15.31	30.67
3	1.19	2.39	4.79	9.66	19.30	38.28
4	0.79	1.58	3.17	6.38	12.88	25.37
5	0.93	1.85	3.68	7.46	14.89	29.80
6	1.28	2.56	5.03	10.31	20.71	41.15
7	0.76	1.52	3.02	6.07	12.28	25.21
gen.	0.84	1.68	3.35	6.74	13.61	27.37

Table 2: Allocation comparison for generated parser and its prototypes. Columns represent allocations (in Gb) required to process input file according to file size (in Mb).

1	2.71	5.43	10.88	21.83	43.76	87.63
3	2.88	5.77	11.56	23.20	46.50	93.10
4	2.13	4.26	8.55	17.18	34.46	69.02
5	2.25	4.51	9.04	18.15	36.41	72.92
6	2.94	5.89	11.80	23.68	47.46	95.02
7	2.23	4.46	8.95	17.98	36.05	72.21
gen.	2.42	4.85	9.74	19.54	39.18	78.47

```

parseUser userStart =
  if s_index bs userStart == '<'
    && s_index bs (userStart + 1) == 'u'
    && s_index bs (userStart + 2) == 's'
    && s_index bs (userStart + 3) == 'e'
    && s_index bs (userStart + 4) == 'r'
    && s_index bs (userStart + 5) == '>'

```

377 **Parser 5** Parser 5 retains the ‘working memory’ of IORef for each attribute
 378 or element type that is held in the output structure. In order to conserve
 379 memory, it then constructs a record only upon element closure.

```

parser :: ByteString -> IO TopLevel
parser str = do
  levelRef <- newIORef (0::Int)
  -- IORef holding each field in the schema
  usersRef <- newIORef Nothing
  userRef <- newIORef Nothing
  -- ... similar code for each field...
  flip Xenoprocess str (Process
    { openF = \tagName -> do

```

Table 3: Memory consumption (in Mb) comparison for generated parser and its prototypes. Columns represent memory consumption (in Mb) need to process input file with respective size in header (in Mb).

1	0.26	0.52	1.31	2.62	5.23	10.45
3	0.42	0.82	1.63	3.24	6.48	12.95
4	0.21	0.39	0.77	1.57	3.27	6.60
5	0.21	0.43	0.88	1.78	3.57	7.13
6	0.51	1.00	1.97	3.90	7.78	15.56
7	0.12	0.24	0.47	0.94	1.87	3.74
gen.	0.13	0.25	0.50	0.99	1.98	3.96

Table 4: Count of garbage collections of generated parser and prototypes

1	2.66	5.32	10.67	21.41	42.93	85.96
3	2.87	5.75	11.53	23.14	46.40	92.93
4	2.20	4.40	8.82	17.72	35.54	71.18
5	2.29	4.59	9.20	18.47	37.04	74.18
6	3.01	6.02	12.07	24.22	48.54	97.18
7	2.23	4.47	8.96	17.99	36.11	72.35
gen.	2.45	4.90	9.81	19.66	39.47	79.09

```

level <- readIORef levelRef
case (level, tagName) of
  -- Here we dive into structure
  (0,"users") -> writeIORef    levelRef 1
  (1,"user" ) -> writeIORef    levelRef 2
  -- Store nested values
  (2,"uid"  ) -> writeTextToRef uidRef
  -- ...similar code skipped...
, closeF    = \tagName -> do
  -- Construct whole record
  level <- readIORef levelRef
  case (level, tagName) of
    (2, "user") -> do
      let name = Nothing
          uid  <- readIORef uidRef
          name <- readIORef nameRef
          bday <- readIORef bdayRef
          -- ...similar code skipped...
          modifyIORef' usersRef (Users {..} : )
          -- back to previous level
          writeIORef levelRef 1
      -- ...similar code skipped...

```

```

    })
    Just users <- readIORef usersRef
    return users

```

380 **Parser 6** Parser 6 uses data reification of event streams (SAXEvent type) and
381 passes the resulting tokens to Parsec ([37]) parser combinators.

```

parser :: ByteString -> Either String TopLevel
parser = first errorBundlePretty . parse parseUsers "" . Xenom.process

type SaxParser a = Parsec Void [SAXEvent] a

parseUsers :: SaxParser Users
parseUsers =
  withTag "users" (Users <$> parseUsers)

parseUsers :: SaxParser Users
parseUsers = many parseUser

parseUser :: SaxParser User
parseUser = withTag "user" $ \_ -> User <$> tagValue "uid"
                                     <*> tagValue "name"
                                     <*> tagValue "bday"

-- Collection of useful combinators
withTag :: ByteString -> SaxParser a -> SaxParser a
withTag tagName sp = openTag tagName *> sp <*> closeTag

tagValue :: (F.MonadFail m, MonadParsec e [SAXEvent] m)
          => ByteString -> m ByteString
tagValue tagName = do
  void $ satisfy (==OpenElt tagName)
  -- ...auxiliary code skipped...

```

382 **Parser 7** Parser 7 uses a single mutable vector, similar to that used by Xenom.DOM
383 offsets (and Parser 3), to add inlined string comparisons (of Parser 4). This
384 parser allows for lazy output extraction.

```

parser :: ByteString -> Either String TopLevel
parser = fmap extractTopLevel . parseToArray7

parseToArray7 :: ByteString -> Either String TopLevelInternal
parseToArray7 bs =
  Right $ TopLevelInternal bs $ UV.create $ do
    vec <- UVM.unsafeNew $ BS.length bs
    _ <- parseUsers vec
    return vec

```

```

where
  -- Some parser just parse tags and
  -- call parser for nested tags
  parseUsers vec = do
    UMW.unsafeWrite vec 0 0
    let usersStart = skipHeader bs 0
        if   idx bs usersStart      == ord '<'
            && idx bs (usersStart + 1) == ord 'u'
            && idx bs (usersStart + 2) == ord 's'
            && idx bs (usersStart + 3) == ord 'e'
            && idx bs (usersStart + 4) == ord 'r'
            && idx bs (usersStart + 5) == ord 's'
            && idx bs (usersStart + 6) == ord '>'
        then do
            (_, usersEndStart')
            - <- parseUser 0
              $ skipSpaces bs (usersStart + 7)
            let usersEndStart =
                skipSpaces bs usersEndStart'
            if   idx bs usersEndStart      == ord '<'
                && idx bs (usersEndStart + 1) == ord '/'
                && idx bs (usersEndStart + 2) == ord 'u'
                -- ...skip similar code..
            then
                return $ usersEndStart + 8
            else
                failExp "</users>" usersEndStart
        else
            failExp "<users>" usersStart
            -- ...skip similar code...
    -- At the end final value parsers store
    -- reference to value in result array
    parseUid arrayUidStart uidStart' = do
      let uidStart = skipSpaces bs uidStart'
          if   idx bs uidStart      == ord '<'
              && idx bs (uidStart + 1) == ord 'u'
              && idx bs (uidStart + 2) == ord 'i'
              && idx bs (uidStart + 3) == ord 'd'
              && idx bs (uidStart + 4) == ord '>'
          then do
              let uidStrStart = uidStart + 5
                  uidStrEnd = skipToOpenTag bs uidStrStart
              if   idx bs uidStrEnd == ord '<'
                  && idx bs uidStrEnd == ord '/'
                  -- ..skipped...

```

```

    then do
      UMV.unsafeWrite vec arrayUidStart uidStrStart
      UMV.unsafeWrite vec (arrayUidStart + 1)
                        (uidStrEnd - uidStrStart)
      return $ uidStrEnd + 6
    else
      failExp "</uid>" uidStrEnd
  else
    failExp "<uid>" uidStart
  -- ...skip similar code...

extractTopLevel :: TopLevelInternal -> TopLevel
extractTopLevel (TopLevelInternal bs arr) = Users extractUsers
  where
    extractUsers =
      let count = arr `UV.unsafeIndex` 0
          in User $ map extractUser
              $ [1,(1 + userSize)..(1 + userSize * (count - 1))]
      -- ...skip similar code...
    extractUser ofs = User
      { uid = extractMaybeXmlString ofs
        -- ...skip similar code...
      }

```

385 In order to identify the best implementation, we manually coded seven differ-
 386 ent parser prototypes. Table tbl. 1 compares the speeds of the generated parsers
 387 and their prototypes, while tbl. 2 and tbl. 3 compare memory consumption, and
 388 tbl. 4 counts prototype garbage collections. Since Parser 2 is slow and consumes
 389 a large amount of memory, it is disregarded for the rest of the analysis.

390 Parser 7 was selected as our code generator template. We here encapsulate
 391 operations within combinators to make the parser code easier to read, and we
 392 present a section of example generated code:

```

parseTopLevelToArray
  :: ByteString -> Either String TopLevelInternal
parseTopLevelToArray bs =
  Right $ TopLevelInternal bs $ V.create $ do
    vec <- V.new $ BS.length bs `div` 7
    let parseusers vec = do
        V.write vec (0::Int) (0::Int)
        (_, _) <- inOneTag "users" $ parseusersContent 0
      return ()
    where
      parseUserTypeContent arrStart strStart = do
        (arrOfs1, strOfs1) <- inOneTag "uid" strStart $ parseInt arrStart
        (arrOfs2, strOfs2) <- inOneTag "name" strOfs1 $ parseString arrOfs1

```

```

        (arrOfs3, strOfs3) <- inMaybeTag "bday" arrOfs2 strOfs2 $ parseDay
        return (arrOfs3, strOfs3)
    parseusersContent arrStart strStart = do
        (arrOfs1, strOfs1) <- inManyTags "user" arrStart strStart
            $ parseUserTypeContent
        return (arrOfs1, strOfs1)
    -- ...auxiliary code skipped...
    parseusers vec
    return vec

-- | Extractor of haskell data
-- from internal array
extractTopLevel
    :: TopLevelInternal -> TopLevel
extractTopLevel (TopLevelInternal bs arr) =
    fst $ extractUsers1Content 0
    where
        extractUUserTypeContent ofs =
            let (uid, ofs1) = extractIntContent ofs in
            let (name, ofs2) = extractStringContent ofs1 in
            let (bday, ofs3) = extractMaybe ofs2 extractDayContent
            in (UserType{..}, ofs3)
        extractUsers1Content ofs =
            let (user, ofs1) = extractMany ofs extractUUserTypeContent
            in (Users user, ofs1)

```

393 **Parsing combinators** We next define the combinators that are needed for
394 efficient input parsing:

```

ensureTag :: Bool          -- ^ Skip attributes
          -> ByteString    -- ^ Expected tag
          -> Int           -- ^ Current offset in the input
          -> Maybe (Int, Bool)

inOneTag, inManyTags, inMaybeTag, inManyTagWithAttrs
    :: ByteString          -- ^ Expected tag
    -> Int                 -- ^ Current offset
    -> Int                 -- ^ Output array offset
    -> (Int -> Int -> Parser (Int, Int)) -- ^ Nested tag parser
    -> Parser (Int, Int)

```

395 To ensure that high-level code does not hinder performance, we first bench-
396 marked an ‘intended result’ from a small schema code generator.

397 **Final generated code** In the parser generated from the schema, we simply
398 represent them as code flow sites, since this token handling is inlined implicitly
399 by the code generator.

400 The following example code uses actual parser combinators:

```
parseUsersContent arrStart strStart = do
  (arrOfs1, strOfs1) <-
    inManyTags "user" arrStart strStart
    $ parseUserTypeContent
  return (arrOfs1, strOfs1)
parseUserTypeContent arrStart strStart = do
  (arrOfs1, strOfs1) <-
    inOneTag "uid" strStart $ parseInt arrStart
  (arrOfs2, strOfs2) <-
    inOneTag "name" strOfs1 $ parseString arrOfs1
  (arrOfs3, strOfs3) <-
    inMaybeTag "bday" arrOfs2 strOfs2 parseDay
  return (arrOfs3, strOfs3)
```

401 This code does not need to store field offsets within the <user> content
402 structure; this is because both parser and extractor use constant offsets that are
403 consistent with XML Schema. Thus, representation is dictated by the resulting
404 data structure rather than by the original placement of elements within the input
405 structure.¹⁰

406 We now examine how the parser works. As illustrated in fig. 1, the parser
407 meets the node <users>. Since it can contain a sequence of sub-nodes, the
408 parser reserves the current position and starts to analyze the sequence.

409 Next, the parser ensures that the next node is a <user>, and it then meets
410 with node <uid>42</uid> and writes the offset (50) to string "42", and its
411 length (2) to an offset array. The parser then goes to <name> and writes offset
412 71 and a string length of 4, "John", to the offset array. The parser does the
413 same for node <bday>, writing offset 95 and length 10.

414 The parser now switches to the next node: <user>. After processing the
415 <user> node, the parser writes 147, 3 for "777" and 169, 5 for 'Lucky'. Since
416 the node <bday> is optional and not included in this example here, the parser
417 returns 0, 0.

418 Finally, the parser meets the close tag </users> and writes the sequence
419 length of 2 at its initial place before proceeding to fill the offset array. The
420 resultant data structure can be extracted lazily from the offset structure using
421 extraction combinators:

```
extractUserTypeContent ofs =
  let (uid, ofs1) = extractIntContent    ofs in
  let (name, ofs2) = extractStringContent ofs1 in
  let (bday, ofs3) = extractMaybe      ofs2
      extractDayContent
  in (UserType{..}, ofs3)
```

¹⁰ Although this does not apply to elements with mixed content, it is sufficient for data mapping purposes.

```

extractUsersContent ofs =
  let (user, ofs1) = extractMany      ofs
      extractUserTypeContent
  in (Users user, ofs1)

```

422 We now consider how extraction of Haskell datatype `user` extraction (intro-
423 duced in sec. 2.3) works.

424 As illustrated in Figure 1, the extractor first reads 2 from the offset array
425 and reads two `User` objects. In order to read each `User` object, the extractor first
426 reads the offset to a piece of string as well as the string length and it then parses
427 this information to the appropriate type:

428 The field `uid` of the first `User` is formed from the 2-byte long string that is
429 extracted from the 50th byte. The field name is then formed from the 4-byte
430 long string that is extracted from 71st byte. If the `<bday>` offset is zero, the
431 extractor returns `Nothing`, and if the offset is non-zero, the extractor will attempt
432 to extract `<bday>` from a specified offset and length.

433 Note that the resulting structure does not use any unsafe pointer operations,
434 since all pointers are encoded as offsets.

435 4 Benchmarking

Table 5: Speed comparison for generated parser and other tools. Columns represent the time (in seconds) required to process the input file according to the respective header size (in Mb).

xeno	0.03	0.07	0.13	0.26	0.53	1.08
pugixml	0.05	0.09	0.20	0.40	0.81	1.63
hexml	0.03	0.06	0.11	0.28	0.56	1.26
hexpat	2.71	5.45	10.94	21.65	43.40	91.73
lxml	0.35	0.70	1.40	2.81	5.64	11.30
xml-typelift	0.04	0.08	0.17	0.33	0.66	1.33

436 4.1 Main alternatives

437 For benchmarking purposes, we developed a short program that simply gener-
438 ates XML files of similar structures, but with different file sizes and containing
439 random data. Six files of the following sizes (in Mb) were generated: 32, 64, 128,
440 256, 512, and 1024.

441 Our tools seem to show a clear linear scaling according to input size (see
442 tbl. 5). Note that the C-based `hexpat` tool performs more slowly than any of the

Table 6: Allocation comparison (in Mb) for generated parser and other tools. Columns represent allocations (in Gb) required to process input files according to the respective header size (in Mb).

xeno	0.03	0.07	0.13	0.27	0.54	1.08
pugixml	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
hexml	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.50	1.00
hexpat	6.16	12.33	24.66	49.36	98.76	197.56
xml-typelift	2.42	4.85	9.74	19.54	39.18	78.47

Table 7: Total memory consumption (in Mb) comparison for generated parser and other tools. Columns represent memory consumption (in Mb) required to process input files according to the respective header size (in Mb)

xeno	0.06	0.13	0.25	0.50	1.00	1.99
pugixml	0.14	0.29	0.58	1.15	2.31	4.61
hexml	0.09	0.19	0.37	0.74	1.47	2.94
hexpat	1.74	3.45	6.88	13.59	27.07	52.79
py-lxml	0.28	0.28	0.56	1.13	2.25	4.50
xml-typelift	0.13	0.25	0.50	0.99	1.98	3.96

443 other tools that were tested, especially for large files. In particular, the C-based
 444 **hexpat** tool took 91.7 seconds to process the 1 Gb file, while the other tools
 445 processed the same file in under two seconds. This result further reinforces our
 446 point that clever implementation is more important than language choice when
 447 optimizing tool performance; thus, developer skill and experience are essential
 448 to producing high performance solution.

449 All our tested tools demonstrated linear growth between file size and common
 450 allocated memory and GC (see tbls. 6, 7, 8); this growth had a direct correlation
 451 with performance.

452 5 Discussion

453 This parser contributes to evidence [38] that advanced compilers of high-level
 454 languages can have similar performance (speed) to those of low-level languages
 455 provided that the software developer is sufficiently well-skilled.

456 Although parser speed can be improved through innovative implementation
 457 and optimization, neither approach is used in the Glasgow Haskell Compiler
 458 (GHC) or its LLVM. Given the importance of string processing, it is disappoint-
 459 ing that neither GHC or LLVM implement inline keyword matching, and we
 460 recommend that this is pursued in future work.

461 This paper presents techniques for high-level processing of xxx, without com-
 462 promising memory use or processing speed. Our results confirm that effective use
 463 of high-level language libraries enables performance to match that of low-level

Table 8: Count of garbage collection cycles for generated parser and other tools using Haskell garbage collection.

xeno	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.08
hexpat	6.32	12.65	25.31	50.66	101.36	202.77
xml-typelift	2.45	4.90	9.81	19.66	39.47	79.09

464 languages, while at the same time maintaining safety and retaining interface con-
 465 venience. We expect that implementation of these techniques will be expanded
 466 into high-performance parsers in the future. Offset-based encoding of pointer
 467 structures suggests a number of interesting future research directions in GC;
 468 region-based GCs would possibly help in this case.

469 6 Future work

470 While our goal was to develop a tool suitable for a wide range of uses, implemen-
 471 tation of entire XML Schema is beyond the scope of this paper; not all features
 472 are currently supported (`xs:element` references, `xs:import`), and isolated cases
 473 remain untested.

474 Our future work includes adding new functionality that will be designed
 475 to not hamper performance when used in the most common circumstances. In
 476 particular, we plan to facilitate incremental data extraction, without building
 477 intermediate data structures, by implementing XPath. Provided we secure suf-
 478 ficient funding, we might also implement a monoidal parallelization scheme for
 479 the parser, in the spirit of the hPDB parser [38].

480 Although we have not yet modeled mixed content, it would be relatively
 481 easy to map mixed content as a list of sum types (ADT) that contain all al-
 482 lowed elements, and text node constructors. We also plan to add mmap and null
 483 termination pre-allocations to the XML Typelift, just as we did with `xeno`.¹¹

484 Since `VectorizedString` operations are only exposed in `Xeno.DOM` and its
 485 generated parser, it would be interesting to formally demonstrate their correct-
 486 ness.

487 7 Conclusion

488 While XML documents validated by XML Schema definitions are valid, in order
 489 to analyze these formats in a typed programming language, XML data types
 490 must be converted from XML Schema into meaningful language data type dec-
 491 larations, and parsers must be generated for these XML documents.

¹¹ More accurately, we will add ‘mmap’, since it will allow us to take advantage of
 the significant virtual memory that is available from a 64-bit processor and, thus,
 map the entire input directly to memory. This will allow the operating system to
 implicitly manage the paging-in of the input, as required.

492 We presented a Haskell tool that converts XML standard data types into
493 Haskell data types, thus making this data available for analysis by Haskell pro-
494 grams. A key advantage of our tool is that it allows easy handling of large XML
495 Schemas, such as Office OpenXML, by Microsoft Office applications.

496 XML TypeLift avoids the complexities of XML parsing and validation by
497 directly mapping valid input documents into correct Haskell datatypes that rep-
498 resent the intended domain. In a sense, *XML mapping to Algebraic Datatypes*
499 (*XML-ADT mapping*), behaves just like object-relational mappings, which are
500 used for interfacing OOP programs to relational databases; this prevents type
501 mismatches (detected at compilation), allowing effective utilization with XML
502 document parsing. Programmers can, thus, use the full power of the type sys-
503 tem for conversion of XML Schema data types to Haskell data types, since type
504 validation is performed prior to compilation. Invalid documents that cannot be
505 parsed to Haskell data types return an error message that identifies the error
506 location.

507 Even though similar parsing solutions exist within other Haskell packages,
508 such as HXT, XML TypeLift offers the following key advantages: (i) It performs
509 online input processing without using system memory. (ii) It has fast, low mem-
510 ory usage and event-based parsing using pure-Haskell `xeno` parser. (iii) It runs
511 fast for small and large document data processing libraries in other languages
512 [28, 34, 39]

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